

BIOWAX IMPREGNATION OF FLEXIBLE PACKAGING PAPERS WITH HIGH TRANSPARENCY AND RECYCLABILITY

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Abstract: *Papers are preferably used as renewable materials for flexible packaging where barrier resistance, transparency, and recyclability are required. In replacement of traditional transparent packaging papers with integrated window of a polymer film, a new method has been optimized by local impregnation of the paper with biowax in an industrial roll-to-roll process. In this study, a range of biowaxes was screened in relation with their processing conditions to improve transparency of impregnated papers. However, the paper structures impregnated with a hydrophobic biowax and intimate interaction between cellulose fibers, might pose challenges in the recycling: the fiber clogging and permanent deposition of wax during repulping may possibly interfere with the recycling process. Following the Harmonised European laboratory test method to generate parameters enabling the assessment of the recyclability of paper and board products in recycling mills with conventional process (Part I)", version February 2024, it has been successfully demonstrated that impregnated biowaxes papers give positive technical recyclability scores (T = 91 to 98), with extremely high total fiber yield (> 99 %). In parallel with optimizing impregnation and recycling processes, the intrinsic properties of selected biowax types remain critical for best performance.*

Keywords: paper, packaging, transparent, recyclable, impregnation, biowax.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union's Single-Use Plastics Directive represents a landmark policy aimed at reducing the environmental impact of plastic waste, particularly from items designed for single use (EU 2019/904). While the directive primarily targets plastic products, it also addresses plastic-coated papers by encouraging the development and adoption of sustainable alternatives, while their functionalities as a flexible packaging material should remain (Lin et al., 2012). In this context, recyclable transparent papers are emerging as a promising substitute for conventional plastic films used in packaging, labelling, and wrapping, or flexible electronics, sensors and light-emitting devices (Ling et al., 2020). The use of innovative materials from cellulose and renewable sources may offer transparency and barrier properties while being compatible with paper recycling streams and promoting circular material flows.

As the opacity of conventional papers originates from the interaction of light with the heterogeneous structure of a porous fiber network causing scattering effects at the fiber-air interface, the micro-voids between the fibers may be reduced by calendering (Vernhes et al., 2009), internal crosslinking (He et al., 2024), or impregnation with substances of comparable refractive index (Asayama et al., 2024), such

as cellulose nanofibers (Huang et al., 2023), vitrimer polymers (Zhang et al., 2022), glycerol (Wang et al., 2022), polyvinyl alcohol (Zhao et al., 2023), or alternative thermosetting resins, such as limonene acrylates, and epoxy (Song et al., 2025). The ecological packaging papers through impregnation with bio-waxes were still less explored (Jasiolek et al., 2021). As a replacement for traditional multimaterial papers with integrated transparent window of a polymer film, they can be developed at industrial scale for practical applications with preferential recyclability (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Illustration for application of biowax-impregnated paper as flexible bread bag with high transparency.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Samples

An overview of reference materials and impregnated paper samples evaluated in this study is given in Table 1. A standard packaging grade paper (Flexpack Smooth, Starkraft, Pöls, Austria) with base grammage 35 g/m² was utilized as reference material of bleached kraft paper from 100% virgin fibers (sample 1). The glassine paper typically used as transparent paper grade (Crystal™ Flexible, Ahlstrom-Munksjö, Espoo, Finland) with available base grammage of 32 g/m² is used as an industrial reference material available for transparent packaging applications (sample 2).

The standard papers were impregnated with either (i) a single type of synthetic “paraffin” wax (sample 3), and (ii) different types of biowax (samples 3 to 9), either covering one or two sides of the paper. The impregnation of a paper roll was done on an industrial pilot-scale roll-to-roll set-up under confidential conditions of temperature, pressure and contact times that were internally optimized in order to achieve maximized transparency. The non-disclosure of detailed processing conditions and wax compositions does not interfere with further implementation of the test results in this study, focusing on characterization of optical properties and recyclability of the impregnated papers.

Table 1: Sample characterization of impregnated papers with different types of biowax

Sample number	Side 1		Side 2	
1	Reference non-impregnated paper			
2	Glassine paper			
3	Synthetic wax	8.0 g/m ²	-	
4	Palm wax	8.0 g/m ²	-	
5	Sunflower wax	8.0 g/m ²	-	
6	Rapeseed wax	8.0 g/m ²	-	
7	Castor wax	8.0 g/m ²	-	
8	Castor wax	4.5 g/m ²	-	
9	Castor wax	4.5 g/m ²	Castor wax	3.5 g/m ²

2.2 Testing Methods

The optical properties of the paper samples were evaluated in terms of standard transparency measurements (ISO 2471:2008 Paper and board — Determination of opacity (paper backing)), and gloss measurements (ISO 8254-1:2009 Paper and board — Measurement of specular gloss). The transparency was determined on a UV-2450 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan), reporting the transmission value (%) in relation to a reference measurement on a fully transparent polymer film. The paper samples were measured with the incident light beam directed towards the impregnated

side of the paper. After recording the UV/VIS spectra in the wavelength region between 200 to 900 nm, the transmission value was determined at selected wavelength of 600 nm. The gloss was measured with a microgloss meter (BYK-Gardener Instruments, Geretsried, Germany) at an incident light angle of 80° normal to the paper surface, after calibration on a black reference sample. All transparency and gloss measurements were repeated at five places over an A4-size paper surface and reported as average values.

The recyclability was evaluated following the "Harmonised European laboratory test method to generate parameters enabling the assessment of the recyclability of paper and board products in recycling mills with conventional process (Part I)", version February 2024. In short, the repulping of a 50 ± 1 g dry sample at a stock consistency of 2.5 % (total volume 2 liter) was done in a disintegrator (TLS TechLab Systems, Lezo, Spain) compliant with ISO 5263-1 at temperature = $40 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 7 and number of revolutions = 30,000 corresponding to a minimum required time of 10 min. The screening was done for a pulp stock sample of 1.5 liter poured on a Somerville screen (TLS TechLab Systems, Lezo, Spain) without addition of a thickener. The coarse screening was performed while using a perforated plate containing holes with 5 mm diameter and a water flow of 8.6 l/min for 5 minutes. The fine screening was performed while using a plate with slots of 150 μm width and a water flow of 8.6 l/min for 20 minutes. The weight fractions of coarse rejects (CR) and fine rejects (FR) were determined after filtration and drying and reported as a percentage with respect to the dry weight of the sample. The results are expressed as a technical recyclability score (T) calculated according to the protocol from the total screening yield score (TSY), visual impurity score (VI) and sheet adhesion score (SA). A schematic summary of the operations for disintegration, screening and sheet formation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Flow diagram for recyclability assessment and evaluation of coated paper samples.

The microscopic images of impregnated paper samples and laboratory handsheets made from coarse accepts (CA) and fine accepts (FA) were made on a confocal laser scanning microscope at objective magnifications of 20x and 50x.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Paper sample evaluation

The surface morphology of wax-impregnated papers is visualized in Figure 3, with various coverage of the surface and interfiber pores depending on the wax type and grammage. In contrast with traditional coatings processes, the impregnated papers do not have a continuous surface coating owing to the relatively low amounts of applied wax. The concentration of waxes corresponding to the required filling grade of the pores at both paper sides was calculated from a theoretical model for mesoporous

paper (Zhu et al., 2015) in line with the practically applied grammage of 8 g/m². The further analysis for chemical compatibility between the wax and fibers did not indicate chemical interactions.

The resulting transparency and values of surface gloss for the different wax-impregnated papers are summarized in Figure 4, indicating favorable increase in transparency relatively to the non-impregnated base paper (Figure 4a) and highest transparency for selected biowax types with either one- or two-sided impregnation (sample 7) approaching the values of 80 % for industrial transparent paper grades (sample 2). The latter confirms a good saturation of the pores in the paper structure though impregnation of the biowax at given concentration. The maximized gloss value (Figure 4b) for biowax impregnated papers exceeds industrial reference samples and confirms the formation of a homogeneous smooth surface after one-sided impregnation at highest wax concentration (sample 7).

Figure 3: Microscopic evaluation of surfaces for reference papers and wax-impregnated paper samples.

Figure 4: Optical evaluations of wax-impregnated paper samples, with (a) transparency (%) determined from UV/VIS spectroscopy, (b) gloss measurements with microgloss meter on side 1 (blue bars), side 2 (brown bar).

3.2 Recyclability assessment

The different parameters resulting from the recyclability assessment are given in Table 2. The total fiber yields are high (TSY > 98.5%) for best performing biowax impregnated papers (sample 5, 6, 7, 8, 9), as compared to synthetic wax (sample 3, TSY = 98.1 %) and industrial transparent paper (sample 2, TSI = 97.0 %). The main differences are seen in a strong reduction of coarse fiber rejects for biowax impreg-nated papers due to the absence of fiber clogging during repulping in contrast with poor recyclability of traditional wax-coated papers (Yadav et al., 2024). The sheet adhesion tests did not reveal any tackiness for all samples (SA level 1 corresponding to SA score 0): the handsheet can be separated completely from the carrier board and cover sheet without any damage or breakages.

As a result, the total recyclability scores T = 91 to 98 (samples 4, 5, 6, 7) for biowax impregnated papers exceed the acceptance limit T > 80, and perform better than papers with synthetic wax with (sample 3, T = 83). The recycling of papers with synthetic wax was also complicated by the deposition of a thick wax slurry in the water effluent after repulping. Main differences in T scores are observed by the influences of wax grammage and single/double sided impregnation (samples 7, 8, 9). The reduction in fine rejects for biowax impregnated papers is visually confirmed by the residues on the screen (Figure 5a, 5b), including single fibers and partly disintegrated sample material. The quality of the handsheets from coarse accepts and fine accepts (Figure 5c, 5d) indicates non-fibrous material impurities for samples 2, 3, 4 and high fiber qualities for samples 5, 6, 7 and 8. The visual impurities (VI score) can mainly be related to presence of few small translucent particles, according to a general overview of the quality of handsheets made from fine accepts with different VI scores (Figure 6).

Table 2: Test results of recyclability assessment

Sample number	CR (%)	FR (%)	TSY (%)	VI score	SA score	T score
1	0.00	0.00	100	0	0	100
2	2.10	0.90	97.0	-5	0	80
3	1.02	0.85	98.1	-15	0	83
4	1.10	0.80	98.1	-5	0	91
5	0.53	0.78	98.7	-5	0	91
6	0.42	0.65	98.9	0	0	98
7	0.00	0.30	99.7	-5	0	94
8	0.20	0.30	99.5	-15	0	84
9	0.20	0.50	99.3	-15	0	84

Figure 5: Evaluation of different fiber fractions after screening of the repulped fibers, (a) fine rejects (RF) on the 150 µm screen collected from sample 2 (synthetic wax), (b) fine rejects (RF) on the 150 µm screen collected from sample 7 (biowax), (c) microscopic evaluation of handsheets made from coarse accepts (AC), (d) microscopic evaluation of handsheets made from fine accepts (AF).

Figure 6: Illustration of handshets from fine accepts with different VI scores, (a) VI level 1 (VI score 0, e.g. sample 6), (b) VI level 2 (VI score -5, e.g. sample 4), (c) VI level 3 (VI score -15, e.g. sample 8).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The biowax-impregnated papers provide a valuable alternative for flexible packaging papers with local insertion of transparent areas. Depending on the processing parameters and selection of appropriate biowax types, competitive transparency with industrial paper grades is demonstrated in parallel with superior recyclability scores. The technology can be upscaled for roll-to-roll processing in industry.

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